

PYTHON DASTURLASH TILI AFZALLIKLARI

Mirzarahmonov Hojiakbar Dilshodjon o'g'li

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Python dasturlash tili sodda va o'qilishi oddiy bo'lgan dasturlash tili bo'lib u inglizcha so'zlarni qo'llab quvvatlaydi kalit so'zlar o'rnida shuning uchun bu boshqacha ko'rinishga ega. Python Interpretori: Bu tarjimon tomonidan ish vaqtida qayta ishlanganligini va uni bajarishdan oldin dasturni kompilyatsiya qilishning hojati yo'qligini bildiradi. Bu PERL va PHP ga o'xshaydi.

Python Interaktiv: Bu siz aslida Python buyrug'ida o'tirib, dasturlarni yozish uchun to'g'ridan-to'g'ri tarjimon bilan aloqa o'rnatishingiz mumkin degan ma'noni anglatadi.

Python Ob'ektga Yo'naltirilgan: Python Ob'ektga yo'naltirish uslubini yoki dasturiy texnikasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Python Boshlovchilar tili: Python – boshlang'ich dasturchilar uchun ajoyib til bo'lib, oddiy matnni ishlashdan WWW brauzerlariga o'yinlarga keng ko'lamdagi ilovalarni ishlab chiqishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Ushbu ilmiy maqolada Python dasturlash tilining boshqa dasturlash tillaridan sodda va kengayuvchanligini ko'rib chiqamiz. Python dasturlash tili imkoniyatlari kengayishiga moyil bo'lgan

dasturiy til hisoblanadi.. Bundan tashqari, Python juda ham ko'p, foydali hamda xilma-xil dasturlar kutubxonalarga egaligi ham juda muhimdir.

Python interaktiv dasturlash tili bo'lib, ob'ektga yo'naltirilgan tillar jumlasiga kiradi, ya'ni, Python ob'ektga yo'naltirish uslubini yoki dasturiy texnikasini qo'llabquvvatlaydi. Python boshlovchi dasturchilar tilidir, ya'ni u boshlang'ich dasturchilar uchun ajoyib til bo'lib, oddiy matnni ishlashdan tortib, veb-brauzerlaridagi o'yinlarga qadar keng ko'lamdagi ilovalarni ishlab chiqishni qo'llab quvvatlaydi. Python ning buyruqlari va sintaksisi ABC, Modula-3, C, C++, Algol-68, SmallTalk va Unix shell kabi boshqa ko'plab tillardan va skript tillaridan olingan. Python mualliflik huquqi bilan himoyalangan. Xuddi Perl kabi, Python dagi manbaa kodi GNU General Public License (GPL) ostida mavjud. Pythonning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari quyidagilarni o'z ichiga qamrab oladi:

- *O'rganish oson*: Python nisbatan kam sonli kalit so'zlar, oddiy tuzilish va aniq belgilangan sintaksisga ega;
- *Tushunish va o'qish oson*: Python kodi juda aniq va yodda qoladigan tarzda yoziladi;
- *Unda ishlash juda ham qulay*: Python ning muvaffaqiyati – manba kodining tuzilishi juda sodda va tushunarli;
- *Python kattagina standart kutubxonaga ega*: Python ning eng qudratli jihatlaridan biri kutubxonaning asosiy qismi juda portative va UNIX, Windows va Macintoshda o'zaro faoliyat platformalar bilan mos keladi;
- *Interaktiv usulda ishlash imkoniyati mavjud*: Python da terminalda ishlash uchun juda qulay, natijalarni terminalda test qilib ko'rsa ham bo'ladi;
- *Bu til moslashuvchan hisoblanadi*: Python keng apparat platformalarida ishlaydi va barcha platformalarda bir xil interfeysga ega;

- *Kengaytirilish imkoniyatlariga ega:* Python tarjimoniga past darajadagi modullarni qo‘shishingiz mumkin;
- *Ma’lumotlar bazalari bilan ishlash qulayligi:* Python barcha a’lumotlar bazasini qo‘llab quvvatlaydi;
- *GUI dasturlashni amalga oshirish imkoniyati:* Python Windows MFC, Unix, X Window kabi platformalarga GUI dasturlar tuzishni qo‘llab quvvatlaydi;
- *Moslashuvchanligi:* Python qobiq buyruq fayliga qaraganda, katta dasturlarga yanada yaxshi moslashish va ularni qo‘llab-quvvatlash imkonini beradi;
- *Funksional va tuzilgan dasturiy usullarni va Ob’ektga yo‘naltirilgan dasturlashni qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi;*
- *Buyruq fayli sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin* yoki katta ilovalar yaratish uchun bytekodga to‘planishi mumkin;
- *Juda yuqori darajadagi dinamik ma’lumotlar turlari* va dinamik turdagi tekshiruvlarni qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi;
- Chiqindilarni avtomatik ravishda to‘plashni va ularni tozalashni qo‘llabquvvatlaydi (*musorosborshik funksiyasi*);
- C, C++, Java va PHP kabi dasturlash tillari bilan osonlik bilan bog‘lanishi mumkin.

Python dasturlash tili boshqa tillarga nisbatan o‘rganish ancha oson va shu bilan birga imkoniyatlari boy bo‘lgan til hisoblanadi. Ya’ni, til o‘rganishni boshlovchilar uni osonlik bilan o‘rganishlari mumkin, shu bilan bu til yordamida ancha-muncha jiddiy amaliy loyihalarni ham amalga oshirish mumkin.

Python haqida quyidagi uchta xulosaga kelish mumkin:

1. Python dasturlash tilining keng miqyosda qo‘llanilishi mumkin bo‘lgan uch asosiy soha bor: veb-dasturlash (*backend – vebserver uchun ilovalar yozish*), sun’iy intellekt masalalari, kompyuterda foydalanuvchi juda ko‘p marta bajaradigan mayda ishlar (*elektron xatlarni jo‘natish, fayllarni izlash va bosmalash, elektron jadvaldan biror-bir ma’lumotlarni ajratib olish va xakozolar*).

2. Python o‘rganish ancha oson bo‘lgan dasturiy tildir. Agar tabiiy tillar bilan o‘xshatish qiladigan bo‘lsak, biror-bir tilda fikrni yetkazish uchun ma’lum vaqt so‘zlarni, tilning grammatikasi o‘rganish kerak bo‘ladi. Qandaydir minimal bilim shakllangandan so‘ng, asta-sekin inson o‘z fikrini ifoda eta boshlaydi. Dasturlash tillaribilan ham holat xuddi shunday. Biror dasturlash tilida amaliy foyda keltiradigan dastur yozishni boshlash uchun ma’lum bilimlar majmuini egallash kerak, shundan so‘nggina dasturlashni boshlash mumkin. Boshqa dasturlash tillaridan farqli ravishda, Python da amaliy ahamiyatga ega dasturlarni ishlab chiqishga ancha ertaroq, hali tilning kattaqismini o‘rganmasdan turib ham kirishish mumkin.

3. Python interpretatsiya qilinadigan dasturiy til. Dasturlash tillarini interpretatsiya qilinadigan va kompilyatsiya qilinadigan dasturlash tillariga bo‘lishadi. Aniqroq aytganda, agar dasturlash tilidagi dasturni bajarish interpretatsiya orqali amalga oshirilsa, bunday tillar interpretatsiya qilanadigan til deyiladi. Agar dasturlash tilidagi dasturni bajarish uchun uni avval mashina tiliga o‘tkazish talab qilinsa, bunday tillar kompilyatsiya qilinadigan tillar deyiladi. Aslini olganda, kompyuter uchun yozilgan har qanday dastur interpretatsiya

qilinadi. Chunki mashina kodlaridagi dastur kompyuterning miyasi bo'lgan protsessor tomonidan interpretatsiya qilinadi.

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